

ANISOGRID COMPOSITE LATTICE STRUCTURES FOR SPACECRAFT AND AIRCRAFT APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY: The paper is concerned with Anisogrid (Anisotropic Grid) composite lattice structures whose load-bearing shell is formed by systems of geodesic unidirectional composite ribs made by automatic wet winding process. Developed about 25 years ago for spacecraft application, Anisogrid structures are now under serial production in the Russian Central Research Institute for Special Machinery and demonstrate high weight and cost efficiency in comparison with rib-stringer stiffened traditional aluminum prototypes and their composite analogues. Existing methods of design, analysis and manufacturing of Anisogrid structures are summarized and discussed in application to aerospace structures.

Particular emphasis is placed on the correspondence between the Geodesic structural concept developed for wooden and metal airplanes more than 60 years ago and modern Anisogrid composite structures. It is advocated that the combination of the geodesic airframe structures whose load-bearing capacity is provided by the system of properly directed ribs and the Anisogrid technology which allows us to make unidirectional composite ribs with extremely high specific strength and stiffness by continuous winding can result in the structures whose weight and cost efficiency is considerably higher than is demonstrated by traditional stiffened structures (made of metals or composites).

KEYWORDS: aerospace structures, commercial airplanes, lattice structures, composite materials, filament winding.

INTRODUCTION

Modern composite materials whose high specific strength and stiffness are utilized in spacecraft and rocket structures to a sufficiently high extent are now on the way to be widely used in primary airframe structures of commercial airplanes. Existing experience shows that direct substitution of carbon-epoxy composites for traditional ring-stringer stiffened aluminum airframe structures results usually in 10-20% weight reduction accompanied by considerable cost increase. Taking into account that modern unidirectional carbon composites, being loaded along the fibers, are characterized with specific strength and stiffness which are at least by the factor of 3 higher than the corresponding characteristics of aluminum alloys, one can conclude that the available weight saving is much lower than can be expected. The reason for this situation is associated with specific structural and manufacturing features of traditional airframe rib-stringer stiffened structures which, being made of carbon composites, are sometimes referred to as Black Aluminum (BA) structures. First, the structure of the skin and the stiffeners of BA structures is not unidirectional – the skin and the ribs usually consist of unidirectional or sometimes fabric layers with different orientation angles and have efficient mechanical characteristics which are close to those of aluminum alloys. Second, the weight saving that can be expected for such structures due to lower density of composite material in comparison with aluminum is usually not reached because of relatively low level of allowable strain which is reduced in design of composite structures because of low deformability of unidirectional composites experiencing tension across the fibers. And third, even though BA structures require usually much less assembling operations than aluminum prototypes, they

cannot be made as completely integral structures, and cost savings gained in assembling do not compensate high cost of carbon-epoxy prepregs which are about 25 times more expensive than aluminum alloys. Thus, it can be concluded that BA airframe structures of commercial airplanes provide rather limited possibility for weight saving, whereas their cost efficiency has yet to be demonstrated. The only real advantage of BA structures is associated with their feasibility – they can be designed and built by methods close to those developed for aluminum airplanes. But it can hardly justify low weight savings and high costs. Further reduction of weight accompanied by cost saving can be reached in composite structures satisfying the following conditions:

- principal load-bearing structural elements should have the unidirectional microstructure of composite materials,
- fabrication procedure should involve completely automated processes and provide completely integral structures.

Because the unidirectional composite can work only under uniaxial loading, the corresponding structural element must be a rib. Aircraft structures whose load-bearing capacity is controlled mainly by the ribs are known for more than 60 years [1, 2] and are referred to as Geodesic structures. In these structures, bending moments, as well as torques and transverse forces, are taken by a system of helical ribs, whereas the skin transfers the aerodynamic and internal pressure to the ribs and provides the proper external surface of the structure. In application to composite structures, Geodesic lattice structures (Anisogrid structures) developed about 25 years ago [3] and consisting of a system of unidirectional carbon-epoxy ribs demonstrate high weight efficiency and are widely used as spacecraft and rocket structures. In conjunction with continuous filament winding, which is the less expensive of the existing processes used to fabricate thin-walled composite structures, Anisogrid lattice structures discussed below satisfy both foregoing requirements.

DESIGN

Cylindrical Anisogrid lattice structures with given diameter D and length L are characterized with six design variables, i.e. (Fig. 1)

- the shell thickness (the height of the rib cross section), h ,
- the angle of helical ribs with respect to the shell meridian, φ ,
- the widths of the helical and the circumferential (hoop) ribs cross-sections, δ_h and δ_c (for the structure in Fig. 1, δ_c is the total width of the adjacent hoop ribs),
- the spacing of the helical and the hoop ribs, a_h and a_c , counted along the normals to the axes.

Fig. 1: Lattice structure

The ribs are the principal load-bearing elements of the structure, whereas the skin the necessity of which can be caused by design requirements, is not considered as a load-bearing element in design of lattice structures. Moreover, the skin thickness, being treated as a design variable, degenerates in the process of optimization because the skin contribution to the structure mass is higher than that to strength and stiffness of the structure. Thus, the optimal lattice structure has no skin, and if the actual structure needs a skin, its thickness and structure are preassigned to meet the structural and manufacturing requirements. Because the most critical type of loading for carbon-epoxy lattice structure is axial compression, the design is performed for the reduced axial force

$$P = T + \frac{4M}{D}$$

in which T is the acting axial compressive force and M is the bending moment.

Three basic methods have been developed to design cylindrical lattice structures for axial compression, i.e.,

- geometric programming [4],
- minimization of safety factors [5],
- numerical optimization [6].

According to the second of these methods, the structure is designed for minimum mass under three constraints providing strength of helical ribs under compression (with the safety factor n_s), global stability of the shell (n_g) and local stability of helical ribs (n_l). Analytically formulated constraints allow us to express the design variables in terms of the safety factors, n , and minimize the structure mass under conditions $n \geq 1$. Optimal parameters

$$\bar{h} = \frac{h}{D} \quad \varphi \quad \bar{\delta}_h = \frac{\delta_h}{a_h} \quad \bar{\delta}_c = \frac{\delta_c}{a_c}$$

are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Optimal structural parameters

case 1	case 2	case 3
$p \leq p_s$	$p_s \leq p \leq p_o$	$p_o \leq p$
$\bar{h} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{48\pi^4 k^2 \bar{\rho}^3}{E_h E_c^3} p^4 \right)^{1/10}$	$\bar{h} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\pi^2 k \bar{\rho}}{E_c \bar{\sigma}} p^2 \right)^{1/4}$	$\bar{h} = \frac{\pi p}{16\bar{\sigma}} \sqrt{\frac{kE_h p_s}{3\bar{\sigma} p_o}}$
$tg\varphi = \frac{1}{2}$	$tg^2\varphi = \frac{p_s}{4p}$	$tg^2\varphi = \frac{p_s}{4p_o}$
$\bar{\delta}_h = \frac{5}{4\pi} \left(\frac{108\pi^2 E_c p^2}{E_h^3 k^4 \bar{\rho}} \right)^{1/10}$	$\bar{\delta}_h = \frac{2}{\pi \sin 2\varphi} \sqrt{\frac{3\bar{\sigma}}{kE_h}}$	$\bar{\delta}_h = \frac{2}{\pi \sin 2\varphi} \sqrt{\frac{3\bar{\sigma}}{kE_h}}$
$\bar{\delta}_c = \frac{\bar{\delta}_h}{2\bar{\rho}}$	$\bar{\delta}_c = \frac{p_s \bar{\delta}_h}{2\bar{\rho} p}$	$\bar{\delta}_c = \frac{p_s p_o \bar{\delta}_h}{\bar{\rho} p^2} \left(\frac{p_o^2}{p^2} - \frac{1}{2} \right)$

Three possible cases exist depending on the normalized loading parameter

$$p = \frac{4P}{\pi D^2} \quad p_s = \frac{48\bar{\sigma}^2}{\pi E_h} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\sigma}\bar{\rho}}{kE_c}} \quad p_o = p_s \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_h\bar{\rho}}{E_c}} + \sqrt{\frac{2E_h\bar{\rho}}{E_c} - 1} \right)}$$

in which $\bar{\sigma}$ is the ultimate stress of helical ribs under compression, k is the local buckling coefficient depending on the boundary conditions at the ends of the helical rib segment l_h in Fig. 1 (for a hinged segment, $k=1$ and for a clamped segment, $k=4$), E is the modulus, ρ is the density, $\bar{\rho} = \rho_c/\rho_h$, subscripts h and c correspond to helical and circumferential ribs, respectively. Cases 1 and 2 correspond to axisymmetric and case 3 – to nonaxisymmetric global buckling. In all three cases, $n_g = n_l = 1$, i.e., both buckling constraints are active. For case 1,

$$n_s = 4\bar{\sigma} \left(\frac{9\bar{\rho}}{4\pi^2 p^2 k E_h^2 E_c} \right)^{1/5} \geq 1$$

i.e., the strength constraint is satisfied with some margin. For cases 2 and 3, $n_g = n_l = n_s = 1$, i.e., the designed structure is the structure of uniform strength. The structure mass can be found as

$$M = \pi D L h \rho_h (2\bar{\delta}_h + \bar{\rho}\bar{\delta}_c)$$

ANALYSIS

Designed lattice structures are analyzed with allowance for the skin, doors, joints etc. by finite-element method based on discrete or continuum models of the structure [3]. Discrete model of a lattice interstage composed of beam-type elements is shown in Fig. 2 (the upper part is a simulator of the adjacent metal section of Proton-M launch vehicle).

Fig. 2: Finite-element model of a lattice structure

MANUFACTURING

The typical manufacturing process involves the following operations

- forming of the silicon rubber elastic coating which has grooves for helical and hoop ribs and is fixed on the surface of the mandrel as in Fig.3 (a),
- wet winding of the ribs and the skin and dry winding of the sacrificed layer providing the pressure compacting the material,
- curing,
- machining of the end rings,
- removal of the mandrel by pulling it out of the structure,
- removal of the elastic coating by pulling it inside the structure as in Fig. 3 (b),
- removal of the external sacrificed layer (Fig. 4 (a)),

The fabricated lattice structure is shown in Fig. 4 (b).

Fig. 3: Installation (a) and removal (b) of elastic coating

Fig. 4: Lattice structure before (a) and after (b) removal of the compacting layer

APPLICATION

Spacecraft Structures

Anisogrid composite lattice structures are successfully used in rocket technology and, being in operation for more than 10 years, demonstrate high performance and weight efficiency. The most highly loaded and large-scale lattice structures are manufactured now for Proton-M Russian commercial spacecraft launcher [7] whose diameter exceeds 4 m.

One of the primary structures of a commercial launch vehicle is the payload attach fitting (adapter) which provides the interface between a rocket and a spacecraft. Weight efficiency of the adapter is extremely important because it separates from the satellite in the orbit. Proton-M carbon-epoxy lattice adapter shown in Fig. 5 has the following characteristics

- larger and smaller diameters 2500 mm and 1300 mm,
- height 900 mm,
- total mass 50 kg in which the mass of the lattice structure is 28 kg,
- design axial compressive force 2 MN,
- axial stiffness 440 KN/mm.

Fig. 5: Lattice composite adapter (a) – winding (b), testing (c) and mode of buckling under compression and bending (d)

Designed by analytical [8] or numerical [9] methods, lattice composite adapters demonstrate more than 40% weight saving with respect to aluminum prototypes. By now, eight successful launches of Proton-M have been undertaken with lattice adapters. One of them, the 303-th launch of June 17, 2004, has resulted in a record for Proton mass of the geosynchronized satellite – 5575 kg [7].

Upper and lower interstages for the second stage of Proton-M are presented in Fig. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6: External (a) and internal (b) views of the upper interstage

Fig. 7: Winding (a) and the inner view of the lower interstage

Application of lattice interstages has resulted in 30% weight reduction in comparison with rib-stringer stiffened aluminum prototypes.

Aircraft Structures

High specific strength and stiffness of modern composite materials, particularly of carbon-epoxy composites, have caused considerable progress in application of composites to commercial airplane airframe structures. Today, composites are on the way to be used not only for secondary structures like control-surfaces, fairings, landing gear doors, etc. or for structures like radomes, horizontal and vertical stabilizers whose loading level is relatively low, but also for heavily loaded primary structures like wing and fuselage structures [10, 11, 12]. However, traditional 10-20% weight savings associated with substitution of carbon-epoxy composites for aluminum structures are considerably lower than could be expected referring to high mechanical characteristics and low density of modern composites.

To be specific, consider a typical carbon-epoxy unidirectional composite having the following elastic properties: $E_1=140$ GPa, $E_2=11$ GPa, $G_{12}=5.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.024$, $\nu_{21}=0.3$; strength under

tension, compression and shear: $\bar{\sigma}_1^+ = 2100$ MPa, $\bar{\sigma}_1^- = 1200$ MPa, $\bar{\sigma}_2^+ = 45$ MPa, $\bar{\tau}_{12} = 70$ MPa, density $\rho_c = 1550$ kg/m³ (subscript 1 denotes the fiber direction and subscript 2 – the orthogonal direction). Typical properties of the aluminum alloy used for airframe structures are as follows: elastic modulus $E_a = 71.5$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu_a = 0.3$, yield stress under tension or compression $\bar{\sigma}_a = 300$ MPa, density $\rho_a = 2700$ kg/m³.

Direct comparison of the foregoing data for composite and aluminum is not consistent, because airframe composite elements have laminated structures consisting of unidirectional plies with different orientation angles. Stringers are usually formed by 80% of unidirectional plies and 20% of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. Calculation in accordance with the lamination theory [13] yields for the efficient modulus of the stringer $E_{st} = 115$ GPa. For the skin, the quasi-isotropic ($0, 90^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ$) structure is traditionally used providing the efficient skin modulus $E_{sk} = 55$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu_{sk} = 0.3$.

Introduce the following structural efficiency coefficients specifying the mass ratio of the composite stringer with respect to the corresponding aluminum having the same shape and designed for the same load [14]

$$\eta_{cn}^{st} = \frac{\rho_c E_a}{\rho_a E_c} \qquad \eta_m^{st} = \frac{\rho_c \bar{\sigma}_a}{\rho_a \bar{\sigma}_c} \qquad (1)$$

The first of these coefficients corresponds to compression and the second – to tension. Subscripts *c* and *a* denote composite and aluminum. Similar expressions for the quasi-isotropic skin panel are

$$\eta_{cn}^{sk} = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_a} \sqrt[3]{\frac{(1-\nu_c^2)E_a}{(1-\nu_a^2)E_c}} \qquad \eta_m^{sk} = \frac{\rho_c \bar{\sigma}_a}{\rho_a \bar{\sigma}_c} \qquad (2)$$

Consider the case of compression. Substituting $E_c = E_{st}$ and $E_c = E_{sk}$ into Eqn.1 and 2 we get $\eta_{cn}^{st} = 0.36$ for the stringer and $\eta_{cn} = 0.63$ for the skin. These results mean that the mass of a composite stringer makes 36% of the mass of the analogous aluminum stringer, whereas for a skin panel, the corresponding value is 63%. As can be seen, a composite skin is much less weight efficient than a composite stringer.

For the case of tension, we should first preassign the allowable stress, $\bar{\sigma}_c$. Calculation of the ultimate strains for the unidirectional carbon-epoxy composite with properties listed above yields $\bar{\varepsilon}_1 = 1.5\%$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}_2 = 0.4\%$. The first of these values corresponds to the fiber failure, and the second specifies the deformation at which the cracks in the matrix appear in the material [13]. Usually, these cracks do not affect the material strength and are allowed in spacecraft structures in which composite materials provide rather high weight savings. However, this is not the case for primary composite structures of commercial airplanes in which the operational strain must not exceed $\bar{\varepsilon}_c = 0.4\%$ (for the material under consideration). Actually, the situation is even worse – at an altitude of 10-11 km typical for commercial airplanes, the temperature is about -60°C , and $\bar{\varepsilon}_c$ can be lower by about 20-30%. Taking $\bar{\varepsilon}_c = 0.4\%$, we get the allowable stress for the stringer $\bar{\sigma}_{st} = 460$ MPa and for the skin $\bar{\sigma}_{sk} = 220$ MPa. Then, the corresponding Eqn. 1 gives $\eta_m^{st} = 0.37$ for the stringer and $\eta_m^{sk} = 0.78$ for the skin. Thus, we can expect the weight saving about 60% for the stringers, about 20% for the skin under tension, and about 35% for skin under compression. Because the skin is much heavier than the

stringers, the average mass reduction is about 30%. This value is further reduced by ribs and rings which are fastened mechanically to stringers or skin panels and by allowance for environmental effects reducing mechanical characteristics of polymeric composite materials. As follows from the foregoing discussion, relatively low weight efficiency of traditional stringer stiffened structures made of composite materials is associated with the load-bearing skin which must have a multidirectionally reinforced structure to resist compression or tension in combination with shear. However, before the metal skin has been developed, the airplanes were actually composite and utilized load-bearing wooden frames and doped fabric skins which were not load-bearing elements. The same design concept was used in metal and composite Geodesic airframe structures [1, 2, 15, 16]. So, it looks natural to combine the Geodesic design concept with the Anisogrid composite technology discussed above. In thus developed airframe structure, the operational loads are taken by unidirectional carbon-epoxy ribs for which the η -coefficient specified by Eqn. 1 is about 0.35. The skin which provides the structure sealing and increases the safety factor is made of carbon-epoxy fabric. The fabric skin allows us to increase the allowable deformation in tension $\bar{\varepsilon}_c$ up to 0.6% (no cracks appear in the matrix of the fabric composite under this strain), and the η -coefficient for the skin which does not buckle under compression is about 0.5. Note that the skin stability is provided by the material type and structure. For example, $\pm 45^\circ$ angel-ply fabric skin has relatively low membrane stiffness which results in relatively low load taken by the skin and relatively high critical stress under compression. In cylindrical lattice structures like shown in Fig. 6 and 7, the weight of even relatively thick skin does not exceed one third of the structure mass. So, the η -coefficient for a lattice fuselage section is about 0.4 which means that the structure is 60% lighter than the aluminum prototype. For actual lattice structures with end rings, doors, joints, etc., the weight saving can be about 40%. Lattice composite fuselage structures are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Carbon-epoxy lattice fuselage section (a) and the fuselage panel (b)

Flat lattice structures shown in Fig. 9 can be used as load-bearing fuselage rings, wing and stabilizer ribs and spars [17], cabin floor, etc.

Fig.9: Composite lattice ring (a) and the wing shear web under testing (b)

Lattice shear webs for wings and stabilizers (Fig. 9 (b)) demonstrate extremely high weight efficiency – they can be several times lighter than aluminum prototypes. A typical stabilizer structure can consist of a system of spars and ribs with unidirectional flanges and lattice shear webs and of $\pm 45^\circ$ fabric skin stiffened with unidirectional stringers placed into the grooves formed in the skin.

Flat lattice structures combine low density with high thickness providing high specific bending stiffness which is necessary for the airplane floor panels.

COST

For commercial aircraft structures, in contrast to spacecraft structures, cost is more important than weight [18]. Moreover, possible weight saving is usually associated with the reduction of the operating cost. Existing methods [19] allow us to calculate that the increase of the payload in accordance with the airframe weight reduction results for a middle-range 300-seat plane in \$950 per 1kg for year.

The main contribution to the cost of a composite structure belongs to carbon fibers. The average cost of the typical carbon-epoxy composite with the properties listed above is about 60\$/kg, whereas the cost of aircraft aluminum alloy is about 5 \$/kg. Thus, the unit of mass for the composite is 12 time higher than for aluminum. Note that this is true only for the so-called *wet* manufacturing processes which include the fiber impregnation. The so-called *dry* processes utilize prepregs whose cost is about 120 \$/kg and which are about 24 times more expensive than aluminum. However, the direct comparison of material cost for unit mass is not consistent, because composites and metals have different densities and different mechanical properties. Introduce the material cost efficiency coefficient as [14]

$$\lambda = \eta \frac{c_c}{c_a} \quad (3)$$

in which η is specified by Eqn. 1 and 2 and c is the material cost per unit mass. Because traditional stringer stiffened airframe structures are made by prepreg lay-up, we take $c_c = 120\$/\text{kg}$ and $c_a = 5\$/\text{kg}$. Then, Eqn. 1, 2 and 3 yield

$$\lambda_{cn}^{st} = 8.6$$

$$\lambda_m^{st} = 15.1$$

$$\lambda_{cn}^{sk} = 8.9$$

$$\lambda_m^{sk} = 18.7$$

As can be seen, the λ -coefficient is much lower than the ratio of material costs, and the quasi-isotropic skin material is more expensive than the stringer material by the factor of about two. For a stringer stiffened structure, λ is about 15 which means that the material consumed by the composite structure is, on average, 15 times more expensive than aluminum. For the ribs of the lattice structures made by wet winding, we take $c_c = 60\$/\text{kg}$ and arrive at the λ -coefficient about 4.2. For the skin made of carbon fabric prepreg ($c_c = 160\$/\text{kg}$) we get λ about 16. Thus, for the lattice composite fuselage section, λ is 7,8 which is about 2 times less than for traditional composite stiffened structure.

In composite technology, the higher by an order of magnitude material cost is expected to be compensated by the integral nature of composite structures requiring less joints and assembling operations than metal parts. If this expectation becomes true, the advantages of Geodesic Anisogrid fuselage composite structures are further enhanced, because the ribs and the skin of the lattice structure form a completely integral part made by continuous winding which is the most highly productive process [20]

CONCLUSION

Geodesic Anisogrid composite lattice structures made by wet filament winding promise considerable weight and cost savings with respect to traditional stiffened composite parts of airplane fuselage, wing and empennage structures.

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